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OVERALL SYNTHESIS

PROJECT BRIEFS

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ERA-NET Cofund on Blue Bioeconomy (BlueBio) – Unlocking the Potential of Aquatic Bioresources

SMARTCHAIN

**Smart solutions for advancing supply systems
in blue bioeconomy value chains**

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Deliverable: D5.4 Circular sustainable business models

Synthesis of overall results from the SMARTCHAIN project

SmartChain
Blue Bioeconomy Solutions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report compiles work for task *T5.4 Innovative business models for blue bioeconomy supply chains*. The SMARTCHAIN project's partners have contributed jointly to this report with summaries from the SMARTCHAIN research.

OBJECTIVES

The objective is to synthesize the SMARTCHAIN project's overall results which are aimed at providing tools and approaches to improve efficiency, sustainability, and circularity in the blue bioeconomy.

KEY FINDINGS

This report compiles nine "*Research findings Briefs*" from the SMARTCHAIN project giving an overview and highlights of the key outcomes. The first one "*Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains*" presents an overview of the project's research activities which were focused on case studies in fisheries and aquaculture. The research findings reflect upon the challenges of the fisheries and aquaculture food value chains and the various barriers to transforming to more sustainable circular business models.

The research on mapping of resource use in Iceland and Norway examined the critical points where food loss and waste (FLW) occur and noted the lack of data on rest raw material (RRM) while identifying the main "*Barriers to higher resource utilization in demersal fish supply chains in Norway and Iceland*".

An innovative approach to "*Robotic manipulation of food objects*" is aimed at providing a tool for sorting of raw material in preprocessing, while the research on optimisation and upscaling of gelatin and collagen from fish skins motivates "*Increased utilization and valorization of marine rest raw materials*".

Optimizing the seafood supply chain: Maximizing efficiency, advancing sustainability, and promoting circularity involves the development of production planning models to optimize the in- and outbound logistics flows of a specific company's production facilities, considering quality, environmental and economic aspects.

Architecture of traceability system includes functional and non-functional system specifications which were defined based on requirement analysis and includes a set of high-level requirements for a blockchain based system.

Evaluation of circularity and sustainability in seafood value chains: A simulation-based analysis is based on system dynamics simulation framework to assess scenarios aimed at enhancing sustainability performance by e.g. reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in the supply systems, while maintaining or improving the quality of the biomasses.

Sustainable resource use: Indicators and stakeholders' perception on barriers to enhancing circularity in seafood supply chains were analysed based on in-depth interviews and review of policy implementation regarding circularity strategies and regulations. Furthermore, regulatory and voluntary sustainability reporting practices of

companies was reviewed and a final synthesis provided insights to *Leverage points for improved circularity in blue bioeconomy systems - fisheries and aquaculture food value chains*

The overall SMARTCHAIN results on the accountability of the use of resources in particular rest raw materials showed that the industry needs to develop further circular business models with a focus on innovative applications of rest raw materials and considerations of circularity criteria (e.g. recycle, reuse, remanufacture, closing resource loops) require more attention, while regulatory and organizational hurdles are prevalent. The synthesis of the outcomes provides the basis to formulate evidence-based policy and practice recommendations.

Each brief contains a list of the respective SMARTCHAIN deliverable reports, scientific publications and key contacts. Further synthesis of the findings is in progress to be published in forthcoming scientific papers.

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A policy brief based on findings in WP1 “Towards higher resource utilization in fisheries”: is available at: https://jpi-oceans.eu/sites/jpi-oceans.eu/files/publications/smartchain_diss_policy_brief_flw_whitefish.pdf

SMARTCHAIN research on blue- bioeconomy

Case studies in fisheries and aquaculture value chains in Norway and Iceland

RRM and FLW

Map biomaterial flows in seafood supply chains, with a focus on rest raw material (RRM) to identify the critical points where food loss and waste (FLW) occurs and their causes (WPI)

Data capturing practices and information flows

Identify important data gaps and explore how the recorded data could be used to improve sustainability and decision making (WPI)

BlueBio SMARTCHAIN Project

Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains

The SMARTCHAIN project duration: Oct. 2021- Sept. 2024 (Extension March 2025).

Multidisciplinary and holistic system approach

The SMARTCHAIN project focused on developing approaches and tools for sustainable utilisation, production planning, logistics optimisation, and traceability to enhance transparency, circularity and sustainable use of bio-resources from catch/harvest throughout the value chain of fisheries and aquaculture products. Industry actors were involved in developing and implementing the SMARTCHAIN solutions and models through case studies.

Supply chain mapping of RRM

The resource utilization in supply chains of demersal fisheries and salmon aquaculture in Iceland and Norway was examined and the hotspots identified where food loss and waste (FLW) occur. The objective was also to explore the status of data capturing practices, identify gaps and promote innovative solutions for utilization of rest raw materials (RRM) to increase the degree of circularity and reduce waste.

Figure 1 The main activities representing the work packages (WPs) of the SMARTCHAIN project

Quality sorting

Develop innovative pre-processing option by sorting of raw material according to quality using robots and AI-models based on visual data, and control (WP2)

Value added products

Develop and upscale high quality marine ingredients (collagen) from fish skins through testing of different types of enzymes and various hydrolysis conditions (WP2)

Production planning

Develop production planning models for optimal utilisation of raw materials (WP2)

System assessment and decision support

Develop simulation framework for supply chain scenarios aimed at enhancing sustainability performance (WP5)

Traceability

Define a set of high-level requirements for a blockchain-based traceability system for seafood supply chains (WP4)

Sorting of raw material by robots and value-added marine ingredients

Development of automated sorting and quality characterization along with optimized production planning is aimed at reducing waste from processing. The SMARTCHAIN project also explores upscaling the production of high value marine ingredients from RRM such as fish skins and heads in collaboration with the industry partner Seagarden.

Figure 2 SMARTCHAIN: Process flow for automated quality characterization and sorting (SINTEF)

Supply chain optimization and simulation

Production planning optimization and simulation models are aimed at performing what-if-analyses for specific scenarios of the demand or supply, like seasonality or environmental improvements, with the objective to optimize the in- and outbound logistics flows of a specific company's production facilities, considering quality, environmental and economic aspects.

The work has been carried out in collaboration with the industry partner BRIM and students from DTU. The mathematical models developed aim to optimize the routing and scheduling of fishing activities undertaken by the company's vessels. The primary objective is to ensure a consistent and efficient supply of fish to the production company, which processes the fish into fillets, fishmeal, and fish oil. The study has underscored the critical importance of optimizing the utilization of raw materials and energy usage in the pelagic fishing industry.

A system dynamics simulation framework was also developed to assess scenarios aimed at enhancing sustainability performance from primary production until end consumer. Improvement scenarios include e.g. reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in the supply systems, while maintaining or improving the quality of the biomasses. The SMARTCHAIN simulation framework enables assessment of the end-to-end effects and enlightens policy makers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, stakeholders, and citizens about potential trade-offs.

Traceability system

Improved traceability and the use of blockchain based technologies can increase the transparency in the supply chain. In the SMARTCHAIN project, the work focused on the architecture of a smart traceability system to enable better transmission of information through the value chain. The goal is to guarantee an unbroken cold chain and improve the transparency, circularity and sustainability of the system. Functional and non-functional system specifications have been defined based on requirement analysis. Then a high-level architecture structured into business, traceability data, blockchain and application layers is proposed with descriptions of the expected functionality of the core components. To ensure end-to-end traceability, changes are

Sustainable resource use and circularity

Analyze drivers and barriers to sustainable circular business models in seafood value chains and assess policy implementation (WP3)

Stakeholder outreach

Multi-stakeholder workshops, dissemination and communication activities (WP6)

needed in current supply chain practices and collection and sharing of all (as much as possible) traceability information is key for true end-to-end traceability.

Sustainable resource use and circularity in seafood supply chains

Sustainability indicators and circularity criteria were reviewed for fisheries and aquaculture supply chains and suitable framework selected along with a dashboard of indicators for assessing the performance of the system solutions. The main goal is to elucidate the opportunities and challenges for further advancement of circular blue bioeconomy activities and strategies. The perceptions of companies, experts and policy makers in Iceland and Norway were explored through in-depth interviews and focus groups to gauge the ways in which they contribute to the circular bioeconomy. Furthermore, drivers and barriers to enhancing circularity and sustainability in aquaculture and fisheries value chains were analysed and policy implementation regarding circularity strategies and regulations was assessed.

SMARTCHAIN dissemination and communication activities

SMARTCHAIN contributes to capacity building by creating awareness, opening opportunities for academic researchers and reach out to a broad spectrum of various stakeholders across countries. The objective is to create a “targeted awareness” regarding SMARTCHAIN results with key players and potential users and inform the target market about the benefits of SMARTCHAIN results. A diverse set of dissemination tools have been applied through Social Media presence, stakeholder workshops and webinars as well as production of videos that facilitate the outreach communications about the project.

Focus of the project is on development of replicable technologies and tools that can be applied to other food supply chains. The results are presented in the project’s deliverables and further dissemination in scientific journals, presentations at international and national conferences and workshops/seminars organised by the partners. The deliverable D5.4 compiles a summary of the key messages of the SMARTCHAIN project.

Key sources for further information

This *Research Sope Brief* is an overview of the SMARTCHAIN project’s research topics.

Further information on the research methods and the findings are summarised in separate *Research Finding Briefs and Policy Briefs* based on the project’s deliverables, conference presentations, webinars and published scientific papers.

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SMARTCHAIN Deliverables

- Mehta, S., Myhre, M., Olafsdottir, G., Jordan, C.M., Thakur, M. (2022). Resource utilization in seafood supply chains: Food loss, food waste and rest raw materials. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D1.1 & D1.2*, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 48 pages
- Strand A. V., Olafsdóttir, G., Saviolidis, N. M., Thakur, M. (2023) Data capture and information flows in seafood supply chains in Norway and Iceland. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and the Norwegian Research Council (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D1.3*, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 62 pages
- Strand A. V., Mehta, S., Myhre, M., Olafsdóttir, G., Saviolidis (2024) Can higher resource utilization be achieved in fisheries supply chains? Status and challenges from Iceland and Norway. D1.4 Manuscript submitted for publication
- Misimi, E. (2024). *Report on D2.1 and D2.2. Approach and Results*. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D5.1*, SINTEF Ocean, 13 pages.
- Ghavamifar, A. & Larsen, A. (2024). Production scheduling. The SMARTCHAIN project cofounded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D2.3*, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 16 pages.
- Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. (2023). Logistics optimization. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D2.4*, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 10 pages.
- Skavang, P. K. (2024) Hydrolysis protocols and product bio and chemical specifications. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D2.5*, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 12 pages.
- Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G. (2022). Sustainable resource use and circularity: Selected indicators. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D3.1*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 33 pages
- Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G, Mehta S., Strand, A.V. Myhre, M.S., and Bogason, S. (2023). Stakeholder engagement. Summary of results from stakeholder engagement activities in fisheries and aquaculture systems The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF). The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D3.2*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 28 pages.
- Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G. et al. (2024) Key leverage points and role of actors: Governance of blue bioeconomy supply chains and scenario approaches for innovative business models. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF). The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D3.3*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík.
- Jiang, S., Gorman, J. (2023). Architecture of traceability system. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D4.1*, SINTEF Digital, Trondheim, 37 pages
- Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. (2023). Simulation model framework. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D5.1*, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 13 pages.
- Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. (2024). Report on scenarios for analysis. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D5.2*, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 13 pages.
- Ghavamifar, A. & Larsen, A. (2024). Simulating the end-to-end supply chain. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D5.3*, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 12 pages.

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SMARTCHAIN – Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains

<https://bluebioeconomy.eu/smart-solutions-for-advancing-supply-systems-in-blue-bioeconomy-value-chains/>
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Innovation Fund Denmark

Technology
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Drivers and causes of FLW

The aim is to identify drivers and causes for FLW in different stages of the fisheries supply chain and identify opportunities to increase the use of RRM.

RRM challenges

The main challenges in full utilization of marine resources are access to RRM considering large exports of whole fish, uncertain profitability in RRM value chains, technology and storage on board insufficient and lack of full traceability.

FLW in seafood supply chains

The majority of FLW in the whitefish industry comes from the sea-going fleet because of discards.

Both Norway and Iceland are important global exporters of demersal fish. Even though most of the harvested fish are from sustainable fish stocks they are fully exploited. It is therefore not a feasible option to increase the harvest, to meet the future global demand of seafood. Simultaneously, there are significant amounts of under-utilised rest raw materials (RRM) during harvesting, such as heads, skins, viscera, as well as prevalent food loss and waste (FLW) in the demersal fish supply chains. To identify barriers and opportunities to increase use of RRM and identify drivers and causes for FLW, we have reviewed literature and conducted interviews with industry representatives, as well as mapping information on data capturing and current regulations in Norway and Iceland governing demersal fisheries.

Defining FLW and RRM

FAO¹ (n.d.) defines 'food loss' as the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decision and action by the food industry, while 'food waste' is defined as a decrease in quality and/or quantity in the retail, service, and/or consumption stage. While food loss originates from volume of the main product, like the filet, originally intended for human consumption, RRM originates from the process of producing the main product, separating out other fractions not commonly used for human consumption. Figure 1 shows the stages in the seafood supply chain and gives a schematic overview of how losses or residual fractions are defined as either "food loss", "rest raw materials" or "food waste".

Figure 1 The generic whitefish supply chain with critical points where losses occur.

Currently, national level data on FLW is not generated on a regular basis which is identified as an important knowledge gap in mapping amounts of FLW. Our findings show that regulatory interventions during catch and improved RRM traceability could

¹ FAO. (n.d.). Food Loss and Waste (FLW) in Fish Value Chains. Food Loss and Waste in Fish Value Chains. <https://www.fao.org/flw-in-fish-value-chains/overview/food-loss-and-waste-in-fish-value-chains/en/>

RRM utilization and export

Currently, Iceland has a higher rate of utilization in the demersal fish sector than Norway due to certain regulatory, economic, and institutional aspects

enhance the utilization of RRM in demersal fish supply chains. Information sharing and collaboration between the fishing fleet, seafood processors and the marine ingredient sector would allow improved resource utilization through better management of supply and demand. Furthermore, development of technology for on-board processing and storage is a potential area of improvement. The majority of FLW in the whitefish industry comes from the sea-going fleet because of discards. The main reason for this is the lack of technological solutions on board of the fleet and financial incentives to bring the raw material ashore.

Differences between Norway and Iceland

Iceland has been leading in exporting prepared products, in particular fresh fish/fillets by air due to a larger investment in technology for filleting and portioning, which have been enabled by an increasing share of vertical integrated companies having control of both the fisheries and the processing stage. Norway on the other hand, with less vertical integrated companies, mainly export whole, gutted fish due to high custom duties on prepared products to important markets (i.e. the EU) and high salaries, making it less profitable to process domestically. Both countries have been trending towards higher utilization, and value-added production of the RRM in recent years. For example, the RRM utilization from Norwegian demersal fish industry have in the last years increased from less than 40% to about 60%, while Iceland has reached around 80% as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Total catch, approximate resource utilization and categories of exported demersal fish products (cod, haddock and saithe in 2021 for a) Norway and b) Iceland (Source: Strand et al., 2024)

Leverage points for enhanced sustainability

To enhance the sustainability of the seafood supply chain, it is necessary to increase the use of RRM, improve decision making, and establish relevant sustainability indicators to assess performance.

Transparency, communication, and information sharing

Companies interviewed state that lack of information on available raw materials and quality is a major barrier towards optimization of production and production planning.

For Iceland, only viscera and a share of the fish heads are discarded at sea and is currently not being utilized while most of the catch and the RRM in cod processing on land is utilized². Norway has been producing fish oil and silage from the fractions that are accepted for human consumption by regulation, because of low consumer acceptance and economics which influence further processing into lower value feed ingredients today.

Overall, there are many similarities in terms of information flows and regulatory environment in the seafood supply chains in Norway and Iceland. However, the vertical integration of fishing vessels and processors which is more common in Iceland show a higher degree of information sharing and better production planning.

Key findings on reducing FLW and increasing the utilization of RRM in demersal fish supply chains

To enhance the sustainability of the supply chain, it is necessary to increase the use of RRM, improve decision making in the supply chain, and establish relevant sustainability indicators. Additionally, increasing transparency within the supply chain is a key element in achieving these goals. Various efficient and advanced technologies are readily available to enhance traceability in the seafood sector. However, current regulations do not mandate companies to utilize these technologies, and the existing economic incentives are not sufficiently enticing for companies to adopt them. The following points were identified as key barriers towards increasing the utilization of RRM in the fisheries supply chain.

- There is currently no information available on volumes of losses/discards of by-catch during catch operations, and there is a need for national level data on FLW generated on a regular basis to map amounts of FLW.
- The development of technology for on-board processing and storage is a potential area of improvement to reduce discards at sea
- Iceland has stricter regulations and economic incentives to facilitate total utilization of the catch, Norwegian fisheries management do have incentives for landing of by catch.
- The industry structure of the whitefish sectors differs in terms of communication and production planning where the Norwegian whitefish sector faces some challenges to enhance the utilization of RRM in comparison to the Icelandic vertically integrated whitefish sector.
- Lack of monitoring and documenting temperature and quality of RRM is a barrier towards further utilization.

² Viðarsson, J. R., Guðjónsson, Þ., & Sigurðardóttir, S. (2015). Report On Current Practices In The Handling Of Unavoidable, Unwanted Catches. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1204294>

Key sources for further information

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Scientific publication:

Strand, A. V., Mehta, S., Myhre, M. S., Ólafsdóttir, G., & Saviolidis, N. M. (2024). Can higher resource utilization be achieved in demersal fish supply chains? Status and challenges from Iceland and Norway. *Resources, Environment and Sustainability*, 100157.

Deliverables:

Mehta, S., Myhre, M., Olafsdottir, G., Jordan, C.M. and Thakur, M. (2022). Resource utilization in seafood supply chains: Food loss, food waste and rest raw materials. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF), and UEFISCDI Romania. *Deliverable: D1.1 & D1.2*, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 48 pages.

Strand A. V., Olafsdóttir, G., Saviolidis, N. M., Myhre, M. S. and Thakur, M. (2023) Data capture and information flows in seafood supply chains in Norway and Iceland. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and the Norwegian Research Council (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D1.3*, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 62 pages.

Conference presentations:

Strand, A.V, Mehta, S*, Myhre, M.S., Ólafsdóttir, G., Saviolidis, N. M., Magnus S. Myhre and Shraddha Mehta (2023). Can higher resource utilization be achieved in seafood supply chains? Status and challenges from Iceland and Norway. International Conference on Resource Sustainability (icRS 2023) August 7-9th 2023, University of Surrey, UK.

Strand, A.V. (2022) Blockchain technology for improving decision making in seafood supply chains. Symposium on Catch Identification technologies. November 2-3 rd 2022, Bergen, Norway

Strand, A. V. and Thakur, M. (2022) Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains. ICCO 2022 - 7th IIR International Conference on Sustainability and the Cold Chain. April 11-13th 2022. Online.

Posters

Mehta, S., Myhre, M., Olafsdottir, G., Carvajal, A. K., Jafarzadeh, S. and Thakur, M. (2022). Food loss and waste in seafood value chains: causes, volumes and environmental cost. 36th EFFoST International Conference 2022.

Webinars:

Myhre, M. S. and Mehta, S. (2022) Can higher resource utilization be achieved in seafood supply chains? Status and challenges from Iceland and Norway. SmartChain Stakeholder Webinar. August 31st 2022.

Strand, A. V. (2022) Current data capturing practices in seafood supply chains in Norway and Iceland - a basis for a blockchain based traceability system. SmartChain Stakeholder Webinar. August 31st Aug 2022.

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SMARTCHAIN – Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains

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Robotic manipulation of food objects

Research Findings Brief

September 2024

Robotic automation

SMARTCHAIN focuses on developing robotic automation solutions for manipulation of food/fish objects.

These efforts aim to improve efficiency, sustainability, and competitiveness of producers/processors across the seafood supply chain.

Innovative approach

By integrating advanced perception and control mechanisms, the robot is capable of handling delicate, deformable objects with precision and care, ensuring minimal damage while optimizing efficiency.

Application of robotic manipulation in Food/Seafood

The growing demand for sustainable food production and handling has highlighted the necessity of robotic manipulation in the food and seafood industries. As global consumption of seafood rises, traditional manual processing methods struggle to meet the demand for efficiency, precision, and hygiene. Robotic automation offers a solution by enabling delicate yet consistent handling of soft, deformable objects like fish and seafood, which are difficult for humans to manipulate quickly and safely at scale.

Automation not only improves production efficiency and reduces labor costs but also minimizes food waste and ensures compliance with strict food safety standards. The integration of robotics into food handling presents a competitive advantage, aligning with the industry's focus on sustainability, resource optimization, and enhanced product quality (Misimi et al. 2018)¹.

The SMARTCHAIN project has addressed these challenges by developing a closed-loop, 4DoF robotic manipulation approach that enables both prehensile (grasping) and non-prehensile (non-grasping) manipulation for the gentle handling of food and seafood objects. This approach leverages RGB-D visual sensors and operates using both eye-in-hand and eye-to-hand configurations, allowing the robot to adapt its manipulation strategies dynamically based on real-time feedback.

By integrating advanced perception and control mechanisms, the robot is capable of handling delicate, deformable objects with precision and care, ensuring minimal damage while optimizing efficiency. This innovative approach addresses the industry's need for gentle and accurate manipulation while aligning with goals of sustainability, reduced waste, and enhanced food safety standards. Through its closed-loop control, the approach continuously refines its movements, contributing to the broader adoption of robotics in food processing and ensuring compliance with modern operational requirements.

¹ E. Misimi, A. Olofsson, A. Eilertsen, E.R. Øye, Robotic Handling of Food Objects by Robust LfD, IROS 2018. Doi: [10.1109/IROS.2018.8594368](https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS.2018.8594368)

Preliminary Findings

Manipulation strategy

A closed-loop, 4DoF robotic manipulation approach enables both prehensile (grasping) and non-prehensile (non-grasping) manipulation for the gentle handling of food and seafood objects

Prehensile manipulation

RGB-D sensor enables the robot to detect the object's shape, location, and pose in real-time

Non-Prehensile manipulation

The robot is controlled to place its gripper over the object and initiate a 4DoF pushing action to slide the object to its desired pose

The preliminary findings of the project demonstrate the effective use of an RGB-D sensor in developing control strategies for both prehensile and non-prehensile manipulation (Figure 1).

For prehensile manipulation, the RGB-D sensor enables the robot to detect the object's shape, location, and pose in real-time. The robot then dynamically adapts its gripper's position and orientation at each iteration in a closed-loop manner, ensuring precision and accuracy throughout the task execution. Utilizing a velocity control mode, the robot leverages a visual servoing approach, which continuously adjusts the gripper's movement and its pose until a successful grasp is achieved. This ensures that the robot can handle objects of varying shapes and sizes with a high degree of flexibility and control.

For non-prehensile manipulation, the robot is controlled to place its gripper over the object and initiate a 4DoF pushing action to slide the object to its desired pose. This process is also performed in a closed-loop, with the robot monitoring and adjusting its actions based on real-time feedback from the RGB-D sensor until convergence is reached. By utilizing the same closed-loop control approach, both manipulation modalities—grasping and pushing—are executed with high accuracy, allowing the robot to perform complex manipulative tasks with minimal error. These initial findings underscore the versatility and adaptability of the developed strategies, highlighting the potential for efficient robotic manipulation of food objects in real-world applications.

Figure 1 4DoF robotic manipulation control scheme

Robotic Automation – Recommendations

The preliminary findings highlight that there is a clear need for greater adaptability across the sector to ensure the successful adoption of robotic-based solutions in the food and seafood industries. This can be achieved through tighter collaboration between research and technology developers (RTD) and industry vendors to create flexible solutions that can be seamlessly integrated into any processing plant. Additionally, leveraging the growing access to data for training AI models [1] are crucial for enhancing learning and control strategies in robotic systems. In cases where data is scarce, the generation of synthetic data offers a powerful alternative for training models, with or without fine-tuning in real-world environments ensuring robust performance [2]. For achieving gentle manipulation, especially with delicate or deformable objects, it is essential to integrate visual and force control systems. This allows robots to adapt their interaction forces to the specific properties of each object, preventing quality degradation [3]. By combining prehensile and non-prehensile manipulation techniques, robots could deliver optimal results in a wide range of handling scenarios, enhancing product quality, efficiency, and competitiveness.

Key sources for further information

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Scientific dissemination:

- Robotic manipulation of food objects. In preparation. Intended for publication in a peer-reviewed publication channel such as ICRA or IROS.

Deliverables:

- Misimi, E. (2024). Robotic manipulation of food objects with 4DoF closed-loop control scheme. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D2.1 and D2.2, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 10 pages.

References

1. O.M. Pedersen, **E. Misimi**, F. Chaumette. Grasping Unknown Objects by Coupling Deep Reinforcement Learning, Generative Adversarial Networks, and Visual Servoing, ICRA, 2020. Doi: [10.1109/ICRA40945.2020.9197196](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA40945.2020.9197196)
2. S. Herland, K. Bach, **E. Misimi**. 6-DoF Closed-Loop Grasping with Reinforcement Learning. IEEE International Conference on Robotic Automation, ICRA 2024. Doi: [10.1109/ICRA57147.2024.10610080](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA57147.2024.10610080)
3. A. Lillienkiold, R. Rahaf, P.R. Giordano, C. Pacchierotti, E. Misimi, Human-inspired Haptic-enabled Learning from Prehensile Move Demonstrations. IEEE Trans. System, Man, Cybernetics: Systems 2022. Doi: [10.1109/TSMC.2020.3046775](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.2020.3046775)

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Increased utilization and valorization of marine rest raw materials

Hydrolysis and product specifications

SMARTCHAIN explores upscaling the production of high value marine ingredients from fish skins in collaboration with the industry partner Seagarden

Rest raw materials

Rest raw materials are the parts of the fish which are not primarily intended for human consumption.

Increased utilization of resources, and valorization of end products, is key to achieving circularity in the seafood sector. We must aim to use fish and their rest raw materials for the highest possible step of the value chain, thus maximizing the value of these resources. Marine ingredients are high-quality components, which are shown to possess beneficial health effects, and can be good alternatives to land-based equivalents.

Rest raw materials and processing

The seafood industry produces a great amount of rest raw material every year, and many actors along the value chain are working hard to increase the utilization and add value to these resources. Rest raw materials are the parts of the fish, which are not primarily intended for human consumption, and includes for instance the head, backbone, trimmings, blood, skin and scales, and viscera. However, these resources can be of high quality and may still be suitable for human consumption if processed accordingly. The different types of rest raw material have different biochemical composition, both based on parts of the fish, and also depending on the fish species itself.

Figure 1 Typical rest raw materials from fish.

There are many ways to process the raw material, depending both on the type of raw material and what it can and will be used for. As mentioned, the biochemical

Marine ingredients

Marine ingredients are in high demand, have a positive health effect and should be used for as high-value products as possible.

composition varies among different fractions of rest raw material and impacts how and for what they are utilized, for optimal use of the different parts. Fishmeal and fish oil are often produced from raw material which is not used for human consumption, such as rest raw material, some small species, or by-catch. Enzymatic hydrolysis is a process more expensive than production of meal and oil, however, the process is gentler towards the raw material, and since the raw material used is typically human-grade and the nutrients are well preserved in the process, the ingredients produced from enzymatic hydrolysis can be used for food and supplements for human consumption. Marine ingredients are in high demand and should be used for as high-value products as possible.

Collagen and gelatin

Proteins are the most important nutritional building blocks of the body, and essential to get enough of through a varied diet. Marine proteins are not only showing several health benefits, but if we are to meet the demand for food and protein which will follow the increasing world population in the years to come, marine resources will play an important role. Collagen and gelatin are terms that you have possibly heard in your everyday life, and which are ingredients of high demand and value.

Collagen is a specific type of protein which can be found in the body of both humans and animals, particularly in bones and cartilage, skin, hair and tendons. In humans, collagen keeps the skin firm. As you get older, the body produces less collagen, and wrinkles are formed. Therefore, collagen is popular as a supplement. In tissues, collagen is made up of long, coiled protein structures. When these are uncoiled, which happens when heat is applied, the long protein chains form what is called gelatin. Gelatin has gelling properties, and is therefore widely used in cooking, for instance in gummy candies, and desserts such as jelly. By adding specific enzymes to gelatin, the long chains are split into smaller peptides, called hydrolyzed collagen peptides. These can have bioactive properties and can be used for high-value application such as supplements and cosmetics, or for medical purposes like wound healing. To extract these proteins from rest raw material such as bone or skin, it is both the gentlest and gives the most yield to do this using heat, and thus extract it as gelatin.

Collagen and gelatin

Collagen is a specific type of protein found in bodily tissues, which can be extracted as gelatin or hydrolyzed collagen peptides and used for various applications in food, supplements and pharma.

Figure 2 Extraction of collagen from tissues to gelatin or hydrolyzed collagen peptides, which can be used for various applications in food, supplements and pharma.

Marine collagen

Today, the gelatin and collagen products on the market are primarily from pigs and cattle. For both religious and dietary reasons there are many people who cannot consume these products. Marine gelatin and collagen are very relevant as alternatives to similar ingredients from land-based animals.

Choosing marine ingredients

In addition to being valuable ingredients, contributing to value-creation from increased utilization of rest raw material, there are also other reasons for choosing marine ingredients. Gelatin for instance, is as mentioned an ingredient in many food and supplement products, such as gummy candy, desserts, puddings and capsules for dietary supplements. Today, the gelatin and collagen products on the market are primarily from pigs and cattle. For both religious and dietary reasons there are many people who cannot consume these products. Marine gelatin and collagen are therefore very relevant as alternatives to these ingredients. In addition, marine ingredients tend to have a lower climate footprint than similar ingredients from land-based animals.

Figure 3 Marine gelatin and collagen can be valuable alternatives to similar ingredients from land-based animals, which are currently dominating in the products on the market.

Key sources for further information

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Deliverable:

Skavang, P. K. (2024) Hydrolysis protocols and product bio and chemical specifications. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D2.5*, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim

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BlueBio SMARTCHAIN Project

Optimizing the seafood supply chain: Maximizing efficiency, advancing sustainability, and promoting circularity

Application of optimization in seafood supply chains

SMARTCHAIN focuses on optimizing the process and supply chain by developing a production planning model for the optimal utilization of seasonal raw materials to analyze and enhance logistics flows.

These efforts aim to improve efficiency, sustainability, and circularity in both logistics and production activities across the seafood supply chain.

The increasing importance of sustainability and the circular economy is being recognized across various industries, including the energy-intensive fisheries sector. With global seafood demand on the rise, there is growing pressure on fisheries to operate more efficiently and sustainably with a strong focus on incorporating circularity principles. Circularity emphasizes reducing waste and extending the lifecycle of resources, which is essential in addressing issues like overfishing and the generation of excessive by-products. The challenge of balancing economic viability with environmental responsibility is becoming increasingly urgent. Traditional fishing and processing practices are proving insufficient in the face of issues like overfishing, high energy consumption, and excessive waste. The industry is now increasingly focused on responsible resource management, where the circular use of resources such as reusing by-products, recycling materials, and reducing energy consumption, becomes a critical competitive advantage alongside regulatory compliance and ethical responsibility (Stevens et al., 2018)¹.

In this evolving context, optimizing operations in the fisheries sector is essential. Companies must adapt to changing market demands and stricter environmental regulations while also managing external factors such as fluctuating fish populations and climate change. Incorporating circularity in the seafood supply chain can enhance sustainability by ensuring that resources are not wasted and that by-products are utilized effectively, whether in secondary industries like biogas production or through innovative uses of fish processing waste. Meeting these demands necessitates maximizing the value of each catch through careful planning and optimization of operations, including vessel routing and scheduling, production processes, and resource allocation. Developing advanced models that support decision-making, enhance resource utilization, reduce energy consumption, and promote circularity is crucial for maintaining profitability and ensuring long-term sustainability.

The SMARTCHAIN project has addressed these challenges by developing several data-driven optimization models to account for both final product revenues, energy costs, and circularity aspects, using Brim hf, a fishing and fish processing company in Iceland, as a pilot case. These models are being used to enhance operational efficiency, financial performance, and resource recovery, reflecting the need for innovative solutions in the fisheries sector. As the industry moves towards more sustainable and circular practices, these models highlight how maximizing resource use and minimizing waste can contribute to a more resilient and circular seafood supply chain.

¹ Stevens, J. R., Newton, R. W., Tlusty, M., & Little, D. C. (2018). The rise of aquaculture by-products: Increasing food production, value, and sustainability through strategic utilization. *Marine Policy*, 90, 115-124.

Data-Driven optimization model

Data driven decision making

The current model enables data-driven decision-making by determining the optimal timing for fishing activities and the most efficient routes for vessels, aiming to reduce oil consumption while ensuring that the fish are landed in the freshest possible condition. This optimization of timing and routing shows potential in minimizing energy usage and maximizing the utilization of landed raw materials, contributing to both operational efficiency and sustainability.

The scheduling and routing of vessels for Brim hf, which processes raw fish into primary products (fillets) and by-products (fish meal and fish oil), is being optimized over a planning period, with seasonality and fish availability as key considerations. While the initial results are promising, this model remains in its early stages, with further development required to refine the approach and incorporate more advanced circularity strategies. Figure 1 illustrates the problem, where vessels are deployed to different fishing areas based on fish availability, with routes designed to minimize energy consumption. After returning to the harbor, the catch is assessed for quality, determining whether it is directed to fillet production (low energy-intensive) or fish meal/fish oil production (high energy-intensive), with each process operating within the constraints of the total allowable catch (TAC). As the model is refined in future phases, it will primarily focus on tactical and operational decision-making, which can significantly influence strategic outcomes over the long term. By optimizing day-to-day operations and resource utilization, the model is expected to support more sustainable and circular fishing and processing practices, ultimately contributing to better-informed strategic decisions that align with long-term sustainability goals.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of vessel scheduling, routing, and processing operations

A verbal description of the optimization model is presented as follows:

Objective: Maximization of Profit

- **Profit** = Revenue - Costs
 - **Revenue** = Revenue from selling primary products + Revenue from selling by-products
 - **Costs** = Oil usage for fishing + Oil usage for processing primary products + Oil usage for processing by-products
- **Subject to:**
 - Vessel routing constraints
 - Scheduling constraints
 - Vessel capacity constraints
 - Production capacity constraints
 - Fuel capacity constraints
 - Fish availability constraints
 - Quota allowance constraints
 - Raw material quality constraints

Scenarios

The scenarios are exploring the effects of fluctuations in key variables such as oil prices, market prices of primary products and by-products, fish availability, the quality of the landed fish, and its utilization rate. Additionally, factors such as vessel sailing speed and catch rate during trips are being analyzed to understand their influence on the operational efficiency.

Scenario analyses

Our scenario analyses are being built through extensive collaboration with Brim hf, allowing us to tailor each scenario to real-world conditions and test how fluctuations in key factors impact both economic performance and sustainability.

Circularity

By incorporating circularity principles such as reducing waste and maximizing the use of by-products, the initial results provide valuable insights for decision-making in dynamic operational environments, helping to align business practices with both financial goals and sustainable resource management.

Strategic planning

Strategic planning should focus on aligning operations to maximize fillet production and enhance overall profitability. Also, by incorporating circularity principles such as maximizing the yield of fish oil by fully utilizing all parts of the catch, can enhance profitability while reducing waste.

Preliminary findings and recommendations

Following the validation and verification of the preliminary optimization model, various scenarios are being examined to assess how changes in market conditions could impact both economic performance and environmental sustainability. These scenarios are being built using real data from Brim hf, ensuring that the analysis is grounded in practical and relevant operational realities.

By simulating these conditions, the model has the potential to inform tactical decision-making, enabling vessel operators and fishing companies to better manage risks, optimize resource use, and adapt to evolving market demands, all while maintaining a strong focus on sustainability and circularity. The following preliminary findings are based on the initial results of the implemented scenarios, with further insights expected as the model continues to evolve and develop.

1) Optimizing vessel routing for cost efficiency

Fuel consumption and oil usage are significant cost factors in vessel operations. Prioritizing nearby fishing areas and shortening trips can reduce fuel costs while preserving the quality of the catch, which enhances raw material utilization and product value. A large portion of operational expenses is linked to vessel operations, making vessel efficiency improvements a key area for cost savings. Optimizing routing, reducing trip durations, and investing in fuel-efficient technologies could lead to substantial cost reductions and improve overall financial performance.

2) Improving raw material utilization

Initial findings from the model indicate that the most effective scenario for boosting economic and environmental sustainability is improving the quality of the landed fish, which directly enhances raw material utilization. This can be achieved by minimizing the duration of fishing trips, as shorter trips result in fresher fish that allow for more effective processing, particularly for fillets, thereby increasing revenue and reducing waste. However, while shorter trips improve fish quality, they also lead to more frequent round trips as vessels need to return to sea more often, which increases overall energy usage. Balancing trip duration and energy consumption is crucial for optimizing both efficiency and sustainability.

3) Maximizing revenue by prioritizing primary product

The preliminary analysis demonstrates that fillet production contributes the largest portion of the company's revenue. Prioritizing the catch for fillet production allows the company to achieve higher financial returns compared to diverting resources toward by-products such as fishmeal and fish oil. This initial finding underscores the importance of ensuring that most of the catch is processed into fillets, where the revenue potential is significantly greater. A key factor in this process is the quality and freshness of the landed fish, which is heavily influenced by the time between catching and landing. The shorter this time, the higher the quality of the fish. Higher-quality fish not only increases the amount processed into primary products, resulting in greater income, but also reduces energy costs, as fillet production is less energy-intensive than by-product production.

4) Recognizing the value of by-products

Initial findings from the model indicate that, although fish oil is produced in smaller volumes compared to fillets, it remains a highly valuable by-product and contributes significantly to overall revenue. Despite its lower production share, fish oil recovery

has been shown to play an important financial role, suggesting that it should continue to be a focus in operations. By strategically balancing the prioritization of fillet production with efforts to optimize fish oil recovery, companies can improve both revenue and sustainability, aligning with circular economy goals.

Optimization in seafood supply chain – Recommendations

The preliminary findings highlight the need for seafood companies to align vessel operations and production processes with financial, circularity, and sustainability goals. To fully capture these benefits, optimization must extend beyond vessel operations to include production and processing. Incorporating circularity principles, such as minimizing waste and maximizing by-product use, is key to improving sustainability outcomes. Streamlining production flows and processing both primary products and by-products is expected to efficiently reduce costs and improve resource utilization. A key area for improvement is the availability and accuracy of fish stock data, which impacts the data-driven model's performance. Technology-driven approaches like AI, machine learning, and satellite data are expected to provide real-time insights into fish availability, enhance vessel routing, reduce overfishing risks, and better align operations with sustainability goals. Integrating advanced data analytics with optimized production processes is anticipated to help seafood businesses remain competitive and resilient in a circular, sustainability-focused market.

Key sources for further information

To discuss the research presented in this brief, please contact: Allan Larsen alar@dtu.dk and Ali Ghavamifar aghava@dtu.dk, DTU Management, Technical University of Denmark.

Scientific dissemination:

An optimization approach for vessel routing and scheduling: Insights from implementation in the Nordic fishing industry. Intended for publication in a scientific journal

Deliverables:

Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. (2023). Logistics optimization. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D2.4, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 10 pages.

Ghavamifar, A. & Larsen, A. (2024). Production scheduling. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D2.3, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 16 pages

Conference presentation:

Ghavamifar, A., & Larsen, A. (2024). From catch to coast: An optimization approach for vessel routing and scheduling in the Nordic fishing industry. 33rd European Conference on Operational Research (EURO), Copenhagen, Denmark.

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Architecture of traceability system

Research Findings Brief

September 2024

Blockchain networks

Blockchain-based traceability integrated with IoT can provide benefits and advantages over traditional traceability systems, such as improved and fine-grain traceability, tamper-proof data, real-time and transparent data sharing, automated compliance to regulatory requirements, and efficient and targeted recall

Requirements and specifications

High-level requirements and system functionality specification have been defined and a high-level system architecture is proposed to facilitate data sharing along the seafood supply chain and the end-to-end traceability

This research finding brief summarizes the SMARTCHAIN's project work on the specifications for a blockchain-based traceability system for use in the seafood supply chains. The motivation for such a system is to improve transparency, circularity, and sustainability. The focus is on data modelling using Unified Modelling Language (UML) 2.0 diagrams and using these as the basis for requirements specifications for a blockchain-based traceability system designed to ensure an unbroken cold chain.

Blockchain is a decentralized, distributed ledger technology that has been applied in many domains and applications. Blockchain networks can be categorized into permissionless and permissioned depending on who can access the network, or classified as public, private or consortium according to how the permissions to write to blockchain are assigned¹. Hybrid blockchains combine private and public blockchain and allow organizations to control what data can be publicly accessible and what is restricted, as well as who can access the restricted data. In hybrid blockchains, confidential information is protected but verifiable when needed. Consortium blockchains have been widely used in supply chain applications.

High level architecture for a blockchain-based traceability system for the seafood supply chain

The input to the requirement analysis consists of; i) *Regulatory requirements* for example, traceability requirements from the food law (EU regulation No. 178/2002) ~~is~~ based on the "one step forward, one step back" paradigm. Blockchain can enable even stronger end-to-end traceability to guarantee an unbroken cold chain; ii) *Literature review* of a number of technical systems published, for instance, user requirements in a similar context are documented by Jiang *et al.* (2022)²; iii) *Experience and knowledge* from previous project work regarding requirements, architecture and system design. Furthermore, the data models are based on interviews and a literature study related to the fishery and aquaculture industry (as documented in SMARTCHAIN Deliverable 1.3). The models are extensible and have been generalized from industrial practices in Norway and Iceland. *The following functionality requirements have been identified:*

- Data & storage management: data collection (manually via GUI & automatically via API); uploading to blockchain; query data from blockchain; off-chain data management (various types of data should be supported, e.g., timeseries, text documents, images, videos).

¹ Cao, B. *et al.*, "When Internet of Things Meets Blockchain: Challenges in Distributed Consensus," *IEEE Netw.*, vol. 33, pp. 133–139, 2019

² Jiang, S. and Ræder, T. B. (2022) "Experience on Using ArchiMate Models for Modelling Blockchain-Enhanced Value Chains," in *The International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022*, Gothenburg Sweden: ACM, Jun. 2022, pp. 375–382. doi: 10.1145/3530019.3531346

High level architecture

The design of the traceability system architecture supporting the functional requirements and specifications, is structured into layers. The main components in each layer are identified and their role and interaction described

- User and access management: generation of unique user IDs; add/delete user; assign roles to users and their associated access rights to data (all data in blockchain is transparent to all participants, but off-chain data may have restrictions).
- Creating links with on-chain data (verifiable using hash codes).
- User/client interaction via an interactive interface, for functions such as showing traceability, product tracking etc.
- Integration with stakeholder ERP systems for automatic data exchange.
- Trace: query & show the history of identifiable/traceable events and state changes (if possible/relevant).
- Generation of traceability QR codes for traceability.
- Track: query & show the status of any product/asset.
- Monitor & alert: monitor the condition and flow of the product/fish along the supply chain and give alerts when abnormalities occur, e.g., if temperature exceeds some limit.

As inspiration for this we have used the architecture of a blockchain-based agri-food traceability designed by Feng *et al.*, (2020)³ and of a food safety system designed by Lin *et al.* (2019)⁴. At the technical level, these have much in common with seafood supply chains. Based on these, we propose a high-level architecture for a blockchain-based traceability system for seafood supply chains based on four layers as illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 High level architecture of blockchain-based traceability system for seafood supply chain (from Deliverable 4.1)

The *Business layer* represents the business activities of stakeholders/actors involved in the whole supply chain from fish catch operation (for fishery) or farming/harvest (for aquaculture) through processing and waste handling to distribution and retail. Key data capture points are identified and associated data to be recorded are modelled in the data models.

³ Feng, H., *et al.*, “Applying blockchain technology to improve agri-food traceability: A review of development methods, benefits and challenges,” *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 260, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121031.

⁴ Lin, Q., *et al.*, “Food safety traceability system based on blockchain and EPCIS,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 20698–20707, 2019.

Traceability data

Data are linked to Traceable Units and traceability events and collected at data capture points. These data give information related to seafood quality, temperature, humidity, freshness, traceability, sustainability and circularity. The data can be collected automatically through connected IoT devices and sensors, integration of existing business systems (e.g., SCM, ERP) or data can be registered manually

The Traceability data layer represents the collection and storage of the traceability/key data as well as communication with blockchain. Each actor can store the traceability data collected using an off-chain data storage locally or in the cloud. Key traceability data with a hash representing the stored data associated with the traceability event will be uploaded to the blockchain (on-chain data storage).

The On-chain/Off-chain data sync component is used to synchronize data between on-chain and off-chain data storage and links the data layer and the blockchain layer. This component extracts key traceability data to be uploaded to the blockchain from the off-chain data storage, generates a hash associated to it and the transaction to be uploaded, and uploads the data to the blockchain. The hash and the reference to the on-chain data is also stored on the off-chain storage for future query and also used to guarantee data integrity. When data is queried via the blockchain, relevant off-chain data storage containing the data is identified and the associated data is retrieved and verified against the hash to ensure that the data is not tampered.

The Blockchain layer facilitates traceability information transparency and improves the security of seafood traceability. Based on the quality data collected from the data layer, smart contracts of blockchain can be used for real-time quality monitoring and control, satisfying the requirements of accountability and traceability. The key components in this layer consist of consensus algorithms, distributed blockchain network and on-chain data storage (the distributed ledger).

Figure 2 Information model based on events for the traceability system (from Deliverable 4.1)

The Application layer consists of various applications that utilize the data collected in the traceability system through the blockchain. Actors in the traceability chain can view the data records (events) along the whole supply chain processes, perform "track and trace" functionality and big data analysis, and facilitate reporting to the authorities. The

Track and trace

The "track and trace" functionality consists of asset management (including definition of Traceable Units) and traceability queries.

QR codes for traceable units

We propose to use QR codes (traceability code) to identify the lowest level of Traceable Units (TRU), such as at pallet level. QR code can be generated for each pallet of fish at the landing stage and attached to the pallet so that the QR code can be used to automatically identify the pallet and collect traceability information along the supply chain, as long as the pallet of fish stays together

Generalized model

The data modelling is generalized from data surveys and analysis based on interviews with several key stakeholders in Norway and Iceland, covering supply chain stages related to fishery (catch operation and landing), aquaculture (farming), primary processing and rest raw material processing.

real-time IoT data collected can facilitate the monitoring of the supply chain and can provide timely alerts utilizing smart contracts when deviation occurs. Furthermore, the user management and access control module provides functionality for managing user roles and their access rights to the specific data stored in the traceability system. In addition, the access control module allows the actors to define what data they possess can be visible to whom. For example, end consumers may be only interested to see the origin of the product and get a confirmation that the product is handled properly along the supply chain, and do not care about the details about how the product is transported, while a distributor may also want to know the details of the logistics and other parameters regarding the product quality, and a processor may only share production details with certain actors under specific terms.

The on-chain data storage module will register traceability event IDs, timestamps and hash values. Relevant key data, such as the traceability key, can also be stored on-chain.

An authorized user can add seafood product information to the system. Users can also manually register traceability events and associated data via the user interface. Traceability can be done at various levels of granularity e.g., at product, batch, pallet or fish level. Users can scan the QR code to enter new data for specific TRU (pallet) and new data collected from sensors can be automatically attached to this TRU via the QR code along the supply chain. When new TRUs are created later, new QR code will be created and attached to the TRU to link relevant data to the TRU.

When users want to track and trace a seafood product, they scan the QR code attached to the TRU. The blockchain will identify the TRU and query all the associated traceability data. The hashes and traceability keys stored on-chain will be used to query off-chain data and verify off-chain data integrity. The verified data can then be returned to the application according to the access control rules so that users can view the associated traceability information that they are authorized to access.

We focus on traceability keys associated with Traceable Units in this report. Traceability codes can be generated for these traceability keys as used in the literature and existing traceability system practices, e.g., a UUID. The primary motivation for this is to be able to uniquely identify the Traceable Units.

Data models of a blockchain-based traceability system

The SMARTCHAIN work focused on data modelling regarding what traceability data shall be gathered at which point and on which level (batch, pallet, product, fish, etc.) in the supply chain and the relationship between data and data sources (see Figure 2). In addition, event types defined in the EPC networks can be considered and integrated in the data model. Requirements on new types of data to be recorded in the system are becoming increasingly common, for example, to include sustainability information in the traceability system to facilitate the assessment of the sustainability of supply chains and products, and to include circularity information in the system with the increasing interest in the circular economy.

End to end traceability

The current data models are limited to details from the primary stages of the seafood supply chains.

To support full end-to-end traceability, more events need to be included in the data model, e.g., activities related to logistics/transport, customs, importer/exporter, distribution and storage

Limitations and Recommendations

Traceability keys for traceable units have been identified in the proposed data models. Globally unique IDs for traceable units, e.g., based on emerging standards, can be generated to facilitate end-to-end traceability.

To ensure end-to-end traceability, changes are needed in current supply chain practices. For example, some of the data required for traceability is not mandatory in current regulations. The collection and sharing of all (as much as possible) traceability information is key for true end-to-end traceability.

In addition, some processors mix fish from different suppliers/vessels into one batch, which breaks the end-to-end traceability as it is not possible to trace back from which supplier a fish from a batch comes from. To ensure finer grain traceability, one-to-one mapping between catches and batches should be ensured.

Key sources for further information

This work has been carried out by SINTEF Digital. Further information on the research presented in this brief, please contact: Shanshan Jiang, e-mail: shanshan.jiang@sintef.no

Deliverable

Jiang, S., Gorman, J. (2023). Architecture of traceability system. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D4.1, SINTEF Digital, Trondheim, 37 pages.

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<https://bluebioeconomy.eu/smart-solutions-for-advancing-supply-systems-in-blue-bioeconomy-value-chains/>
<https://www.sintef.no/en/projects/2021/smartchain/>

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Evaluation of circularity and sustainability in seafood value chains: A simulation-based analysis

Research Findings Brief

September 2024

Simulation framework

SMARTCHAIN focuses on developing a simulation framework to assess the end-to-end effects and potentials of improving processes, logistics, and information flows to enhance sustainability and circularity.

This framework is built on conceptual supply chain mapping, supply chain optimization model, and sustainability and circularity indicators. The generated simulation scenarios are expected to provide decision support to enhance the sustainability performance of seafood supply chain.

The complexity in the aims and objectives for achieving sustainable and circular seafood value chains is immense. Ensuring the sustainable use of resources, minimizing loss and waste, and maximizing profits all place an enormous burden on decision-makers. Traditional linear supply chains, which often prioritize efficiency and profit, typically result in significant environmental degradation, resource depletion, and unsustainable practices. Excessive fishing, the unintentional capture of non-target species, degradation of marine habitats, and inefficient resource utilization during seafood processing and transportation all contribute to the increasing burden on ocean ecosystems. Therefore, addressing sustainability and circularity simultaneously in seafood value chains is vital for mitigating the sector's contribution to climate change, reducing pollution, and conserving biodiversity. The shift towards sustainable and circular seafood value chains is not only a matter of environmental responsibility but also an essential strategy for ensuring the long-term viability and profitability of the seafood industry. As seafood becomes an increasingly important source of protein for a growing global population, the need to develop resilient, sustainable, and circular systems is more pressing than ever (Cooney et al., 2023¹ ; Clair et al., 2023²).

Considering these challenges, there is a growing need to develop a comprehensive framework that facilitates the evaluation of sustainability and circularity within seafood value chains. Such a framework must take into account the interconnected processes and interactions across the entire end-to-end supply chain, from harvesting, production and processing to distribution, consumption, and loss and waste management. By considering these interactions holistically, this framework would enable decision-makers to better assess the environmental, economic, and social implications of different strategies, helping them to balance various sustainability goals. Moreover, this type of framework would make it easier to assess scenario-based analyses, allowing stakeholders to explore potential outcomes of different approaches under various conditions, such as changing regulatory, consumer preferences, or technological advancements.

Our approach in the SMARTCHAIN project tackles these complex challenges by employing a System Dynamics (SD) approach to comprehensively evaluate the interconnections within the seafood value chain. By utilizing SD, we can simulate the impacts of various sustainability and circularity strategies, capturing feedback loops and nonlinear interactions throughout the entire supply chain. This method allows us to explore how different policies and innovations influence both environmental and

¹ Cooney, R., de Sousa, D. B., Fernández-Ríos, A., Mellett, S., Rowan, N., Morse, A. P., Hayes, M., Laso, J., Regueiro, L., Wan, A. H., et al. (2023). A circular economy framework for seafood waste valorisation to meet challenges and opportunities for intensive production and sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 392, 136283.

² Clair, R. S., Pappas, D., Fletcher, C., & Sharmina, M. (2023). Resilient or environmentally friendly? both are possible when seafood businesses prepare for long-term risks. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 408, 137045.

System Dynamics

A simulation approach that models complex systems using feedback loops, incorporating stocks, flows, and auxiliary variables. System boundaries, interactions between modules, and exogenous variables influence the overall system behavior.

Causal loop diagram

Our causal loop diagrams, representing different steps within the fish value system, are rooted in the concept of integrated supply, value, and decision chains. Through the provision of a causal modeling framework, this methodology takes into consideration both linear and non-linear relationships, conducting an analysis of variables' endogenous behavior.

By adopting this comprehensive approach, it effectively meets the fundamental requirements for tackling policy and decision-making challenges in the realm of sustainable fish value chains.

financial outcomes, providing a holistic framework to address the evolving needs of the fisheries sector as it transitions toward more sustainable and circular practices.

System dynamics model

The simulation framework aims to identify key intervention points to enhance the efficiency and circularity of the seafood system. Our goal is to create a model capable of predicting how various factors such as government policies, customer behaviors, and technological innovations affect sustainability within a circular economy context. Focusing on critical points where losses and waste occur within blue bioeconomy value chains, and utilizing the mapping of the seafood supply chain, our SD model is being developed based on a generic seafood value chain structure and sustainability metrics. This model can be customized and tailored for specific scenario analyses, and it allows for the assessment of additional sustainability measures by incorporating more specific features, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Generic seafood value chain

We are developing a simulation framework using SD modeling. An overview of interactions across the seafood value chain has been taken into account, as illustrated in Figure 2. This figure will serve as the foundation for developing the causal loop diagram, given in Figure 3. Considering these interactions and system boundaries, the simulation framework is being developed to assess how sustainability indicators may evolve under various scenarios. The SD simulation model, depicted in Figure 4, is supported by numerous equations that are formulated to define and adjust the interactions within the system. Afterward, the framework is being validated and verified and then scenarios are being developed based on expert opinions to examine how changes in key variables, which could reflect real-life situations, might affect sustainability measures.

Figure 2 Overview of interactions between different modules in the seafood value chain

Model validation

Validation involves presenting the framework to experts and practitioners in the seafood industry to gather feedback and ensure its relevance.

Figure 3 The causal loop diagram

Preliminary findings from the scenario analyses

Here's a concise overview of the scenarios examined using data for cod species, obtained from various sources, along with the initial findings:

Scenario analyses

Based on expert viewpoints, several predictive scenarios are being identified and investigated. To run the SD model, we collected data from expert interviews, online databases, and landing data from the largest sales organization in Norway, covering the majority of white fish landings.

Initial results on Scenario 1: Potential impact of advanced preservation technology on fish quality

This scenario explores how implementing advanced preservation technologies on vessels could improve fish quality and reduce spoilage compared to traditional methods. Early findings suggest that using high-tech preservation may lead to better fish utilization for human consumption, reduce reliance on by-products, and lower energy and water consumption in processing. The analysis indicates that improved fish quality could reduce the need to catch more fish, as more of the catch would be suitable for human consumption, contributing to better environmental sustainability. While the initial investment in onboard technology may impact short-term economic sustainability, in the long term, this could be offset by selling higher-quality fish to end consumers and making more efficient use of the catch.

Initial results on Scenario 2: Balancing processed fish and by-product production through enhanced RRM landings

This scenario explores the potential effects of increasing the ratio of rest raw material (RRM) landings. Preliminary results suggest that while higher RRM landings could enhance by-product production, they may also reduce the amount of processed fish due to storage limitations. Bringing in more RRM could result in fewer fish landings at the harbor, but utilizing RRM efficiently for high-value by-products like collagen and fish oil could offset this reduction. Ongoing work seeks to determine the optimal balance between fish quality and by-product production to improve economic and resource efficiency. In addition, combining this scenario with the earlier one where advanced preservation technologies improve fish quality could help compensate for the potential reduction in landed fish. The higher quality of the fish would allow for more efficient use in human consumption, balancing the decrease in fish landings while enhancing overall economic and resource efficiency.

Simulation-based analysis in seafood supply chain – Recommendations

The initial findings from the scenario analyses suggest the potential to address key trade-offs in the seafood value chain, enhancing sustainability and circularity. Each scenario indicates opportunities for reducing food loss and waste, though challenges in implementation highlight the need for technological innovations to overcome these barriers. Additionally, some scenarios show promise for improving circularity, but further exploration is required to balance sustainability goals with resource efficiency. To fully realize these opportunities, the seafood industry could explore the potential of both data-driven and advanced technological innovations, such as more efficient fishing techniques, improved preservation methods, and automated processing systems. These innovations have the potential to address the implementation challenges. Policymakers might play a pivotal role by promoting the adoption of such technologies and encouraging shifts in consumer behavior toward more sustainable choices. Close collaboration among stakeholders, with a focus on integrating cutting-edge technologies and data insights, could be key to driving meaningful progress in fishing, processing, and sustainability practices across the seafood value chain.

Key sources for further information

To discuss the research presented in this brief, please contact: Allan Larsen alar@dtu.dk and Ali Ghavamifar aghava@dtu.dk, DTU Management, Technical University of Denmark.

Scientific dissemination:

Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. Evaluating sustainability and circularity in the seafood value chain: A system dynamics perspective. Manuscript in preparation

Deliverables:

Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. (2023). Simulation model framework. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D5.1, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 13 pages.

Ghavamifar, A. Larsen, A. (2024). Report on scenarios for analysis. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D5.2, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 13 pages.

Ghavamifar, A. & Larsen, A. (2024). Simulating the end-to-end supply chain. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D5.3, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, 12 pages.

Conference presentation:

Ghavamifar, A., & Larsen, A. (2024). Towards a sustainable circular seafood value chain: A system dynamics perspective. Paper presented at the 11th EurOMA Sustainable Operations and Supply Chains Forum conference, Hamburg, Germany.

Ghavamifar, A., & Larsen, A. (2024). Enhancing sustainability and circularity in seafood value chains using system dynamics. Production and Operations Management Society (POMS) Conference, Istanbul, Turkey.

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Circular Blue Bioeconomy

SMARTCHAIN focuses on circular economy solutions for the blue bioeconomy, including improved utilization of rest raw material (RRM) and minimizing food loss and waste (FLW) in seafood supply systems in Iceland and Norway

The European Commission has defined the bioeconomy as “the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy” with the blue bioeconomy referring to aquatic or marine environments, especially, with regards to novel aquaculture applications and non-food, food, and feed applications.

Blue bioeconomy development can support the achievement of broad societal goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through an emphasis on sustainability, circularity, and innovative approaches.

The circular economy (CE) is a way to increase resource efficiency by intentionally narrowing, slowing, and closing materials and energy flows. Overarching CE principles are resource efficiency, optimizing value of biomass and sustainability (Stegman et al., 2020)¹. A conceptual framework is applied here to visualise the circularity in blue bioeconomy systems such as aquaculture and fisheries (Figure 1). The hot spots where food loss and waste occur have been identified and the circular flows indicate utilization of rest raw material into value-added products and recycling of waste streams into fertilizers and bioenergy.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework for circularity of biomass in aquaculture and fisheries chains (Adapted from Carus, 2017)

¹ Stegman et al. (2020) The circular bioeconomy: Its elements and role in European bioeconomy clusters. Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X, 6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100029>

Indicators

Sustainability indicators were selected from pre-existing frameworks relevant to the topic of circular blue bioeconomy. The COM framework, was at the time (in 2022) insufficient to cover fisheries and aquaculture sectors, and therefore, the FAO's indicators for the bioeconomy were added including criteria of fisheries and farm management, and specific criteria for energy efficiency, waste management and wastewater etc.

Sustainability framework and indicators

The objective in SMARTCHAIN was to select framework and indicators relevant to assess circular blue bioeconomy activities in general and more specifically for fisheries and aquaculture. The primary framework selected was the European Commission's "Sustainability criteria for the blue economy", which was further cross-referenced with the FAO's "Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy" and the GRI standards. The final selection resulted in a dashboard of indicators for the environmental, social, economic and governance dimensions (Deliverable 3.1).

CSR reporting

The non-financial reporting on sustainability performance is becoming increasingly detailed and more common, especially among larger companies

To explore the utility of the selected indicators for circular bioeconomy assessment, CSR reports of companies in the fisheries and aquaculture supply chains in Norway and Iceland were reviewed. Relevant themes from the SDG goals have been adapted, in the reporting, for example, in Iceland the CSR reporting of companies follow a joint policy of social responsibility based on the UN SDG goals (Fisheries Iceland²). The main themes in the reports are on life below water, innovation and development, circular economy, minimizing carbon footprint, energy use and switching to alternative energy sources. Many reports are prepared in accordance with the GRI Standard and ESG reporting guide. Sustainability reports may play an important role as a supporting tool in the transition of organisations towards more circular economy models, since their content can help to measure, monitor, and communicate the organisations' transition and to establish goals in the short/medium term (Ibáñez- Forés et al., 2022)³.

ESRS

The ESRS are a set of new standards and indicators that aim to standardise the way in which companies report on non-financial aspects

Although sustainability has often been defined as depending on three pillars (economic, social, environmental) it has become increasingly accepted that governance must be included among them as a dimension that is crucial to the achievement of sustainability goals. This emphasis is also evident in the private sector's Environment Social Governance (ESG) standards. It is foreseen that the new Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the European sustainability reporting standards

² Fisheries Iceland (SFS) The association's goal is to safeguard the interests of the fisheries sector, including companies in aquaculture. [Ábyrgur sjavarútvegur \(sfs.is\)](http://abyrgur.sjavarutvegur(sfs.is)).

³ Valeria Ibáñez- Forés, et al., (2022). Sustainability reports as a tool for measuring and monitoring the transition towards the circular economy of organisations: Proposal of indicators and metrics (2022). Journal of Environmental Management, 320, 2022, 115784, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115784>

Stakeholder engagement

In-depth interviews and focus groups were conducted to gauge the view of stakeholders in Iceland and Norway on the challenges involved in transforming the fisheries and aquaculture food supply systems towards more sustainable and circular bioeconomic systems

Analytical framework

The data analysis is based on institutional theory and four broad categories,:

- 1) Regulatory (domestic and international regulations, policies, roadmaps, strategies etc);*
- 2) Resources (tangible (material, financial, physical) and intangible (knowledge and skills);*
- 3) Market (customers, consumers, partners or competitors in the value chain, service providers and industry associations);*
- and 4) Social (the community at large, NGOs, local communities, the media, and issues like image and reputation and corporate social responsibility and organizational values)*

(ESRS) will put pressure on the private sector to update their CSR reporting practices which have been relying on national framework references or other standards, such as GRI, SDGs and the UN Global Compact.

The ESRS cover Cross cutting standards on General requirements and General disclosures as well as Topical standards in three areas: 1) Environment: Climate change, pollution, water and marine resources, biodiversity, and circular economy; 2) Social: Own workforce, workers in the value chain, affected communities, and customers and end-users; 3) Governance: Business conduct. The new ESRS standards are tailored to EU policies, particularly the Green Deal, while building on and contributing to international standardization initiatives.

Interviews and focus groups

The main objective of the stakeholder engagement activity was to identify the stakeholders' perception on the drivers and barriers regarding transformation of the food system as well as assessing synergies and trade-offs. Selected findings from the stakeholder activities (interviews, focus groups) are shown in Figure 2. The pie chart indicates how frequently certain topics emerged in the different theme categories. The resource and regulatory issues dominated the discussion in both countries.

Figure 2 Summary and selected findings from stakeholder interviews on the perception of challenges and barriers in Iceland and Norway (Saviolidis et al.2023, Deliverable 3.2)

Circularity in seafood supply chains - Recommendations

A transition towards a circular economy for the blue bioeconomy can contribute to resource efficiency gains which are integral to sustainable development. At the same time, it can also stimulate increased profit by turning waste streams or lower value products into value or higher value streams. Advancing the circular blue bioeconomy can also contribute to internationally agreed upon goals: the SDGs.

One of the major issues that emerged in interviews is the *need for mapping all FLW streams* both in terms of quantities but also in terms of the content and quality of these streams. The findings show that realising the potential of a more circular blue bioeconomy requires the *development of target-based overarching strategies* and the implementation of a *systemic approach cutting across different sectors* (e.g., agriculture, tourism, transport, and energy sector).

Key sources for further information

To discuss the research presented in this brief, please contact: Nína María Saviolidis ninamaria@hi.is and Guðrún Ólafsdóttir go@hi.is, University of Iceland

Deliverables:

Saviolidis, N.M. and Ólafsdóttir, G. (2022). Sustainable resource use and circularity: Selected indicators. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TF). *Deliverable: D3.1*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 33 pages.

Saviolidis, N.M., Ólafsdóttir, G., Mehta S., Strand, A.V. , Myhre, M.S., and Bogason, S. (2023). Stakeholder engagement. Summary of results from stakeholder engagement activities in fisheries and aquaculture systems The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF). The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D3.2*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 28 pages.

Conference presentations:

Saviolidis, N.M., Ólafsdóttir, G., Myhre, M.S., Strand A.V., & Mehta, S. (2023) Drivers and barriers for the advancement of a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland and Norway. International Conference on Resource Sustainability (icRS 2023) August 7-9th 2023, University of Surrey, UK.

Webinars:

Saviolidis, N.M., Ólafsdóttir, G. (2022). Barriers to increased sustainability and circularity in the blue bioeconomy: Preliminary findings Smartchain Stakeholder Workshop/webinar August 31st, 2022 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ocOuQr2VWSQ&t=35s>

Saviolidis, N.M., Ólafsdóttir, G. & Bogason, S. (2023), Barriers to a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland, webinar arranged by an NKJ co-funded network “What do sustainable agro-marine food systems mean in different Nordic contexts?” June 14th, 2023. Nordic Joint Committee for Agricultural and Food Research

Saviolidis, N.M., Ólafsdóttir, G., Myhre, M.S., Strand, A.V., Mehta S., & Bogason, S. (2023) Drivers and barriers for the advancement of a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland and Norway. Smartchain webinar Oct.11th, 2023 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FrWweyAjOCQ>

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BlueBio SMARTCHAIN Project

Leverage points for improved circularity in blue bioeconomy systems - fisheries and aquaculture food value chains

Case studies

The SMARTCHAIN project explores challenges and enablers to circular blue bioeconomy using fisheries and aquaculture sectors in Iceland and Norway as case studies to gauge the status of institutional/ organisational motivation for enhanced sustainability performance

Reduce FLW, recycle and close resource loops

In seafood value chains the focus is on enhancing the utilisation of rest raw materials (RRM) into value added products, minimizing FLW and closing biowaste resource streams to produce e.g. fertilisers and biogas.

The SMARTCHAIN project's case study on "Circularity in the blue bioeconomy value chain" focuses on sustainability criteria and circular bioeconomy objectives. The blue bioeconomy entails the production of renewable aquatic biological resources and the conversion of these resources and rest raw material into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy.

Circularity and sustainability assessment

The identification of common indicators to facilitate transparent communication of sustainability status and circularity improvement potentials is crucial. The topics for CE assessment are closely linked to sustainability in general where the issues on efficient resource use (input – output), waste- and wastewater management, energy use/efficiency and GHG emissions are most common. Circularity and sustainability assessment approaches vary among companies depending on sector, type of activity and size. Tailormade sustainability or circularity indicators based on LCA approach or direct impact are commonly applied and seafood businesses are engaged in collecting data for continuous monitoring of GHG emission performance over time. However, there is a need to identify and monitor additional indicators to ensure the seafood sector develops not only towards climate neutrality but also towards broader sustainability (Ziegler et al. (2024)¹.

The reporting of circularity principles "reuse, recycling, and recovery" is often lacking in sustainability reports, and the disclosures and the relevant KPIs need to be better designed to reflect activities of closing the loop (e.g. recycle, recover), as well as slowing the loops (e.g. reduce, reuse (remanufacture)). This implies that the CE reporting is still weak and lacks standards and guidance for companies who mainly seek to legitimate their own position and actions by reflecting institutional logics that are centered on best practices (Dagiliene et al., 2020)². Generally, improvements in approaches to CE assessment are needed to facilitate a transparent communication of the performance and notably, enhanced collaboration with the upstream and downstream actors and stakeholders involved in the supply chain is crucial to capture the whole life cycle of products and the circular activities.

¹ Ziegler F., Nistad, A.A., Langeland M., Wocken Y., Hognes, E.S., Mehta. S. (2024) Greenhouse gas emission reduction opportunities for the Norwegian salmon farming sector - can they outweigh growth? *Aquaculture*, 581, 74043, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.740431>

² Dagiliene, L., Frenzdel, M., Sutiene, K., Wnuk-Pel, T. (2020) Wise managers think about circular economy, wiser report and analyze it. Research of environmental reporting practices in EU manufacturing companies, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 274,121968, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121968>

Content analysis of CSR reports

CSR reporting

Insights to the organisational approaches to sustainability and circularity was achieved by reviewing CSR reports from large companies in fisheries and aquaculture in Iceland and Norway

The new European sustainability reporting standards ESRS are aimed at facilitating a more comparable approach to sustainability and circularity assessment. The requirements of the ESRS on biodiversity, ecosystem challenges and circularity is partly addressed in CSR reports to date. The aquaculture companies have identified the main biological and nature related risks and formulated their own strategies and targets. KPIs are used to monitor e.g. topics related to animal welfare like escapes, sea-lice, use of medication which are also regulated and monitored. The ecosystem challenges like eutrophication and monitoring of sediments, freshwater use and wastewater discharge and the provision of sustainable feed ingredients are addressed in the sustainability reports. However, the reporting of resource use in terms of volumes of RRM is lacking and circularity reporting is mainly related to recycling of packaging material (plastics) and in the case of fisheries the recycling of fishing gear, while incentives to enhance recycling of biomaterial will need more attention e.g. utilisation of RRM and closing resource loops e.g. use of sludge and biowaste for bioenergy and fertiliser. Moreover, the double materiality concept requires reporting both direct impacts and challenges of the company including Scope 1-3 emissions, as well as possible financial risks from e.g. climate impacts which may originate from suppliers or downstream in the value chain.

Policy relevant to the circular blue bioeconomy

Review of policies relevant to advancing a circular blue bioeconomy in Iceland and Norway and specifically for the fisheries and aquaculture value chains.

Policy landscape

Policies and strategies relevant to the bioeconomy have been formulated at international, regional and national levels. The list is not exhaustive and several topics such as health and nutrition and social equity considerations would need to be better integrated for a blue bioeconomy to achieve broader sustainability goals than those generally defined under circular economy strategies

Region	Document (policy, strategy, report)	Year
International	Global Bioeconomy Assessment: Coordinated Efforts of Policy, Innovation, and Sustainability for a Greener Future (UNEP)	2024
	Realising the circular bioeconomy (OECD)	2018
European	Circular Economy Action Plan (COM)	2020
Nordic	Nordic Bioeconomy Programme: 15 Action Points for Sustainable Change ((NCM)	2018
	Future Opportunities for Bioeconomy Focus on the West Nordic Region (NCM)	2015
	Resilience in the blue bioeconomy: What can COVID-19 teach the Arctic about the impact of crises on value chains? (NCM)	2021
Norway	National Bioeconomy Strategy (MTIF)	2016
	Ocean Strategy (MTIF)	2021
	Sustainable forestry (NIBIO)	2021
	Green alliance between Norway and the EU for climate action and the green transition (OPM)	2023
	Strategy for Green Competitiveness (MCI)	2017
	Marine Biodiversity Strategy (NMCE)	2022
	Norwegian Plastics Strategy, (NMCE)	2022
Iceland	Climate action plan	2020
	National policy on waste reduction /“Saman gegn sóun” (EA)	2016-2027
	Iceland's Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. (MENR)	2021
	Iceland's Policy on Matters Concerning the Arctic Region (MFAI)	2021

Leverage points

The leverage points identified were categorised according to resource, social, market and regulatory challenges and include for example sectoral routines and structure, institutional, technological, informational and supply chain solutions

It is important to include also food systems and food policies when considering relevant policies for the blue bioeconomy especially when focusing on the primary sectors of fisheries and aquaculture whose primary product is fish. Food relates to several important topics beyond environmental impacts and resource efficiency which are the primary focus of circular economy policies, such as health and nutrition, food security, food safety and quality. Shaping policy in such a way that it can integrate these different policy domains that are integral to increasing the sustainability of food systems is crucial (Galli et al., 2020^[3])

Leverage points

The research outcome is a synthesis of the challenges, key leverage points, policy and role of industry actors including the role of respective stakeholders, NGOs and government in the blue bioeconomy supply chain. The focus was on identifying leverage points where improvements can be made to enhance circularity and innovation towards sustainability specifically for the fisheries and aquaculture sectors.

[3] Galli, F., Prosperi, P., Favilli, E., D'Amico, S., Bartolini, F., Brunori, G. (2020) How can policy processes remove barriers to sustainable food systems in Europe? Contributing to a policy framework for agri-food transitions. Food Policy, 101871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101871>

Key sources for further information

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Deliverable:

Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G. et al. (2024) Key leverage points and role of actors: Governance of blue bioeconomy supply chains and scenario approaches for innovative business models. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF). The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). *Deliverable: D3.3*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, xx pages.

Webinars:

Saviolidis, N.M., Ólafsdóttir, G. (2024). Circularity in blue bioeconomy value chains: metrics, challenges and opportunities. Smartchain webinar March 21st, 2024 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ufDki5v9OCY&t=88s>

Scientific publications:

Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G., Strand, A.V., Mehta S., Myhre, M.S., and Bogason, S. (2024). Barriers in the transition to a more circular blue bioeconomy in Norway and Iceland: multistakeholder perspectives. (Forthcoming)

Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G. Key leverage points and role of actors (working title) (Forthcoming)

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SMARTCHAIN – Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains

<https://bluebioeconomy.eu/smart-solutions-for-advancing-supply-systems-in-blue-bioeconomy-value-chains/>
<https://www.sintef.no/en/projects/2021/smartchain/>

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